

BIGUANIDE SULPHATE AS A REAGENT FOR THE ESTIMATION OF COPPER.

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Copper biguanide sulphate, which forms a very sparingly soluble inner-metallic complex salt of the second order, has been utilised for the estimation of copper. Zinc, cadmium, molybdenum (Mo^{6+}), tungsten (W_6^{6+}), magnesium and alkali metals do not interfere with the estimation. The solution must not contain any nitrate as the corresponding copper biguanide nitrate is also sparingly soluble. The precipitate, dried at $50^\circ\text{-}70^\circ$, has the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_4\text{H}_7)_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and is weighed as such. The estimation can be made on both macro and semi-micro scale with very good results, using only a good quality macro analytical balance. In the absence of a large excess of ammonium salt and ammonia the method has also been employed for the volumetric estimation of copper with rubeanic acid as an external indicator.

Complex compounds of biguanide and its substitution products with both bivalent and trivalent metals have recently been studied in detail by Rây and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 670; 1938, **15**, 350, 353; 1939, **16**, 617, 621, 629). They are all inner-metallic complexes of the second order.

The copper biguanide sulphate, which is sparingly soluble at ordinary temperature, is thrown down as a pink coloured, silky precipitate when ammoniacal copper sulphate solution is treated with a solution of biguanide sulphate. The solubility of this complex copper salt at or below 10° is negligible. The precipitate has the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)]_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where BigH^+ = one molecule of biguanide. It can be directly weighed after washing first with water, cooled to below 10° , then with alcohol and ether, and finally drying at $50^\circ\text{-}60^\circ$. Metals like zinc, cadmium, etc. give no precipitate with biguanide sulphate in ammoniacal solution, and copper can, therefore, be easily separated from these metals by means of this reagent. Molybdenum and tungsten, when present in the form of molybdate and tungstate, do not interfere. Metallic ions, which are precipitated by ammonia, *viz.*, iron, aluminium, chromium, bismuth, antimony, mercury, etc., or form insoluble sulphate, namely, lead, calcium, strontium and barium, obviously interfere with the estimation. Cobalt and nickel, which also give rise to sparingly soluble inner-metallic complex salts with biguanide, must be absent. Anions like nitrate, phosphate, ferrocyanide, arsenate, arsenite, etc., whose copper compounds or copper biguanide

compounds are insoluble or sparingly soluble in ammonia, should also be excluded.

It can also be used for the volumetric estimation of copper by titrating an ammoniacal solution of copper sulphate with a solution of the reagent, the end-point being detected by means of an external indicator like rubeanic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Biguanide Sulphate (Reagent).—An intimate mixture of dry dicyandiamide and dry ammonium iodide (1 : 2) was heated on a sand-bath. The molten mass was kept at 173° for five minutes. It was then cooled, extracted with water, rendered ammoniacal and filtered. The filtrate was treated with ammoniacal copper sulphate solution. The precipitated copper biguanide sulphate was filtered, washed and then decomposed with 10% sulphuric acid. On cooling the solution, crystals of biguanide sulphate separated which were recrystallised from water at 60°.

Estimation of Copper as Copper Biguanide Sulphate.

A copper solution was prepared from electrolytic copper and was standardised both electrolytically and by quinaldinate method (Ray and Bose, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1933, 95, 400). To a known volume of the solution, containing no nitrate ion, 0.1 to 0.2 g. of ammonium sulphate was added; it was then treated with ammonia till the solution turned deep blue. The solution was then diluted to 120 c.c., warmed and treated with an excess of biguanide sulphate solution, drop by drop, with constant stirring. A voluminous, woolly, pink-coloured, crystalline precipitate formed at once. The mixture was then cooled in ice to below 10° and allowed to remain at that temperature for about half an hour. It was then filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed first with cold water (10°) until free from sulphate, afterwards with alcohol and finally with ether. It was dried at 50°-60°. The dried precipitate has the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_4\text{H}_7)_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and contains 15.3% copper. Estimations were made on both macro and semi-micro scale. Results are given in Table I, which shows that the amount of copper varying from about 1 mg. to 30 mg. can be determined quite accurately with a good analytical macro balance.

TABLE I.

Wt. of Cu ppt.	Cu found.	Cu taken.	Error.	Wt. of Cu ppt.	Cu found.	Cu taken.	Error.
0.1809 g.	0.02768 g.	0.02765 g.	+0.00003 g.	0.1410 g.	0.02157 g.	0.02157 g.	...
0.1447	0.02214	0.02212	+0.00002	0.2350	0.03595	0.03596	-0.00001
0.1085	0.01660	0.01659	+0.00001	0.2711	0.04148	0.04148	...
0.2170	0.03320	0.03319	+0.00001	0.07175	0.01098	0.01098	...
0.2532	0.03874	0.03872	+0.00002	0.11586	0.01757	0.01757	...
0.2893	0.04426	0.04425	+0.00001	0.1077	0.01648	0.01648	...
0.1989	0.03043	0.03042	+0.00001	0.01085	0.00166	0.00166	...
0.2748	0.04204	0.04204	...	0.00905	0.001384	0.001382	+0.000002
0.2421	0.03704	0.03706	-0.00002	0.0087	0.001327	0.001331	-0.000004
0.1662	0.02543	0.02544	-0.00001	0.007225	0.001104	0.001106	-0.000002

Separation of Copper from Zinc and Cadmium.

The zinc sulphate solution was prepared by dissolving pure zinc in dilute sulphuric acid. The strength of the solution was determined by the quinaldinate method (Rây and Bose, *op. cit.*). The cadmium solution was prepared by dissolving pure $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8/3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in dilute sulphuric acid. The solution was standardised by determining cadmium as sulphate.

The solution containing copper, zinc or cadmium was treated with 1 to 2 g. of ammonium sulphate and then with ammonia till the solution turned deep blue, copper was then precipitated as copper biguanide sulphate as described above. From the filtrate zinc was determined as zinc quinaldinate and cadmium as cadmium sulphate. The results are shown in Tables II and III.

TABLE II.

Wt. of Cu ppt.	Wt. of Zn quin- aidinate.	Copper		Zinc	
		present.	found.	present.	found.
0'1808 g.	0'1582 g.	0'02765 g.	0'02766 g.	0'02420 g.	0'0242 g.
0'2174	0'1742	0'0333	0'0332	0'02662	0'02663
0'1811		0'02765	0'02767		
0'07185	0'1742	0'01098	0'01099	0'02662	0'02662
0'0862	0'4745	0'01318	0'01319	0'07260	0'07256
0'11586		0'01757	0'01757		
0'0862		0'01318	0'01319		
0'1077	0'7908	0'01648	0'01648	0'1210	0'1209

TABLE III.

Cu ppt.	CdSO ₄ .	Copper		Cadmium	
		taken.	found.	taken.	found.
0'2711 g.	0'0971 g.	0'04148 g.	0'04148 g.	0'0573 g.	0'0572 g.
0'2350		0'03596	0'03595		
0'1808	0'1951	0'02765	0'02766	0'1147	0'1149
0'2060		0'03153	0'03152		
0'2203	0'1365	0'0337	0'0337	0'0803	0'0804
0'2280	0'1166	0'0348	0'0348	0'0688	0'0687

Estimation of Copper in Brass.

A sample of brass (0.3 g. approx.) was dissolved in nitric acid. From the solution, tin and lead, if any, were removed by the usual methods. If any iron and manganese be present, they are removed by ammonia and hydrogen peroxide. Copper was then estimated, as described above, in an aliquot part of the solution. Table IV gives the results obtained.

TABLE IV.

Wt of alloy.	Cu ppt.	Cu found.	Cu present.
2.704 mg.	0.01235 g.	69.87%	70.20%
2.329	0.01070	70.30	70.20
5.160	0.0190	56.35	56.6

Separation of Copper from Molybdenum and Tungsten.

The copper solution containing molybdate or tungstate was treated with an excess of ammonium sulphate (1 to 2 g.) and then with ammonia until a clear blue solution was formed. Copper was then precipitated by adding a large excess of biguanide sulphate in the usual way. Copper biguanide, molybdate and tungstate are soluble in ammoniacal ammonium sulphate solution. Results are shown in Table V.

TABLE V.

Cu ppt.	Cu found.	Cu present.	Substance added (in g.).
0.0960 g.	0.01469 g.	0.01472 g.	0.05 Molybdic acid
0.1147	0.01756	0.01766	0.07 Do
0.0384	0.005875	0.00588	0.07 Do
0.0673	0.00103	0.00103	0.50 Sodium tungstate
0.0479	0.00733	0.00736	0.10 Do

Volumetric Estimation of Copper.

When an ammoniacal solution of copper sulphate is treated with biguanide sulphate solution the simple copper ion is converted into the stable inner complex copper biguanide ion, which does not give the usual tests of the former. This has been utilised for the volumetric estimation of copper with the help of rubeanic acid as an external indicator, the end-point is indicated by the disappearance of the reaction for Cu^{++} ions.

Each copper atom is associated with two molecules of biguanide; therefore a normal solution of copper will be equivalent to a molal solution of biguanide sulphate.

The presence of an excess of ammonium sulphate and ammonia exerts a solvent effect producing $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{SO}_4$ in small amount from the complex copper biguanide sulphate, $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}')_2]\text{SO}_4$. Hence, in the absence of a large excess of ammonium sulphate and ammonia, copper can be satisfactorily titrated with biguanide sulphate at or below 10° . Sharp end-points were obtained even with the very dilute copper solutions. Anions and cations (*op. cit.*), which interfere with the gravimetric estimation, must also be excluded here.

Procedure.—The copper sulphate solution was treated, drop by drop, with ammonia until it turned blue. This was then titrated with biguanide sulphate solution with constant stirring. From time to time a drop of the solution was taken out with a glass rod on a quantitative filter paper and

touched with a drop of dilute rubenic acid solution in alcohol and the paper dried by holding it over a Bunsen flame. The end-point was indicated by the disappearance of the black spot on the paper. A more accurate result was obtained by making a duplicate titration adding nearly the whole of the calculated volume of biguanide sulphate solution to begin with and then finishing the titration by testing with the external indicator as described. The results are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Copper soln.	Biguanide sulphate soln.	Copper		Substance added (In g.).
		present.	found.	
100 c.c.	91 c.c.	0'020400 g.	0'02042 g.	...
10	9'1	0'002940	0'002942	...
25	22'75	0'007360	0'007355	...
30	27'35	0'008829	0'008840	...
50	45'66	0'014720	0'01474	...
10	9'3	0'002940	0'002943	0'02 Na tungstate
25	23'3	0'007360	0'00737	0'05 Do
20	18'65	0'005880	0'00590	0'01 Do
10	9'3	0'002940	0'002943	1'0 Zn sulphate
25	23'25	0'007360	0'007359	„ Do
30	27'90	0'008829	0'008830	„ Do

A large excess of ammonium sulphate interferes with the estimation as already stated; this is shown by the results in Table VII.

TABLE VII.

Copper soln.	Biguanide sulphate soln.	Am. sulphate added.
10 c.c.	9'3 c.c.	0'0 g.
10	9'8	2'0
10	10'3	4'0
10	11'4	6'0

In presence of cadmium no sharp end-point could be obtained.